

A HIGH-PRESSURE GAS TPC PROTOTYPE WITH HYBRID CHARGE/OPTICAL READOUT

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1. Introduction

- Neutrino oscillation experiments are often hampered by nuclear medium effects in ν -nucleus scattering events.
- ν -hydrogen interactions are highly desirable due to absence of such effects, but require ingenious detector design [1].
- Gas-phase time projection chambers (TPCs) are suitable due to highly granular track resolution and low energy thresholds [2].
- With the further requirement of radiopurity, gas TPCs are also useful in searches for dark matter [3] as well as $0\nu\beta\beta$ [4].

2. The WarTPC Platform

The WarTPC platform: from the cathode side (left) and the camera side (right).

- The pressure vessel — a 195 litre stainless steel vessel with a maximum operating pressure of 10 bar.
- The TPC — a field cage with a variable drift length up to 42 cm, a double stack of thick gas electron multipliers (THGEMs), and a state-of-the-art TimePix3 camera.
- Among its objectives are: (1) to benchmark TPC performance in different hydrogen-rich gas mixtures, (2) to develop a highly granular hybrid charge/optical readout system and (3) a laser calibration strategy.

3. Charge Readout

Diagram of gas amplification and readout electronics setup.

- Readout electronics — two Cremat CR110 R2.2 preamplifiers connected to THGEM electrode surfaces.
- Shockley-Ramo signals induced on electrodes 1 and 4 give unamplified and fully amplified signals respectively.
- Preamplifier outputs are digitised with a PicoScope 5244D MSO DAQ, enabling construction of pulse height spectrum and gain characterisation.

References

- [1] P. Hamacher-Baumann, X. Lu, and J. Martín-Albo. Neutrino-hydrogen interactions with a high-pressure time projection chamber. *Phys. Rev D*, 102(3), August 2020.
- [2] A. Abed Abud et al. Deep Underground Neutrino Experiment (DUNE) Near Detector Conceptual Design Report. *Instruments*, 5(4):31, 2021.
- [3] E. Baracchini et al. CYGNO: a gaseous TPC with optical readout for dark matter directional search. *Journal of Instrumentation*, 15(07), July 2020.
- [4] K. Mistry and D. R. Nygren. Optimal operating parameters for next-generation xenon gas time projection chambers, 2025.
- [5] <https://www.amscins.com/resources/technology/>. Accessed: 5 January 2026.

4. Optical Readout

Diagram of TimePix3 operating principle [5].

- The TimePix3 readout chip — a 256×256 pixel array CMOS chip with a pitch of $55 \mu\text{m}$.
- Polyethylene naphthalate (PEN) UV-to-visible wavelength shifter and Photonis Cricket intensifier allows for single-photon sensitivity.
- Data-driven suppressed readout gives the time-over-threshold (dE/dx) and time-of-arrival (z-coordinate information) for each pixel.

5. Latest Results

2D histogram of pulse height spectra in electrodes 1 and 4 (left), and relative signal strength with increasing voltage (right).

Integrated optical image in pure Ar at 1.0 bar (left) & 5.5 bar (centre), and 2% methane at 1.0 bar (right).

- Preliminary test with 1.5 kBq Am-241 α source (5.44 MeV peak).
- Quantified charge (top row) and (integrated) optical gain (bottom row) for varying voltage & pressure and increasing CH₄ fraction.
- Gradient of pulse height spectra gives the intra-THGEM gain (e.g. top left figure shows a configuration with a gain of ~ 5).
- Comparing e.g. pure Ar at 1.0 vs. 5.5 bar, or pure Ar vs. 2% methane at 1.0 bar, pressure and methane optical data shows clear drop-off in gain, but fitting procedure needs refinement.

6. Moving Forward

- Development of charge/optical trigger system.
- Full 3D reconstruction of α tracks.
- Addition of scintillating gases e.g. CF₄.
- Fe-55 X-ray source for single electron events for calibration — approval pending!
- Using Moiré effect of stacked THGEMs to probe internal geometry.